

Ecotoxicants from modern industries as a source of environmental and public health risk

Ecotóxicos de las industrias modernas como fuente de riesgo ambiental y de salud pública

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Abstract

The data of study of workplaces of the operator-weigher of raw materials, presser, operator of a chemical site, grinder of chrome shavings was analyzed. At this enterprise mutagenic background is formed due to dibutyl phthalate, sulfuric acid, ethyl acetate, cyclohexane, hydrochloric acid, dioctylphthalene. The risk of development of probable pathology associated with mutagenic activity of production environment factors has been assessed.

Keywords: mutagenic activity, environmental factors, cytotoxicity, ecotoxicants.

Resumen

Se analizaron los datos de estudio de los puestos de trabajo del operario-pesador de materias primas, prensador, operario de un sitio químico, triturador de virutas de cromo. En esta empresa, se forma un fondo mutagénico debido al ftalato de dibutilo, ácido sulfúrico, acetato de etilo, ciclohexano, ácido clorhídrico, dioctileftaleno. Se ha evaluado el riesgo de desarrollo de probable patología asociada con la actividad mutagénica de los factores del entorno de producción.

Palabras clave: actividad mutagénica, factores ambientales, citotoxicidad, ecotóxicos.

Reproductive function is carried out as a complex sequence of physiological processes occurring in the body of the father, mother and fetus¹. The reproductive system is established from the first days of life and is formed under the influence of medical and social factors, among which occupational conditions are of particular importance^{2,3,4}. Chemical toxicants occupy the leading position among harmful and hazardous production factors^{5,6,7}. Toxicants can have adverse effects at any stage of function realization. Cytotoxicity usually underlies germ cell damage¹. The biological action of toxicants is carried out through the receptor apparatus of cells and intracellular structures, and the toxic action is manifested when a minimum number of its molecules are able to bind and affect the most vital target cells⁸.

The Aim of the Study was to assess the level of genotoxicity of the air in the working areas of cardboard and electrical tape production.

In order to achieve the objective, the following **tasks** have to be carried out:

1. Carry out a short-term mutagenicity test of the air in the working areas of the factory.
2. Analyse the data obtained and identify the most unfavourable areas.

The mutagenic activity of environmental factors was assessed by a short-term chromosome and chromatid aberration test according to the Bio-Indication of Environmental Mutagenic Background method No. 05-485, 1993.

Stages of estimation:

1. Mutagenic activity of factors of the working environment
 2. Assessment of induced mutagenesis level of air in working areas of carcinogenic profile facilities
 3. Number of samples taken - 285
- Source matrix 1140 × 8
4. Determine the number of chromosomal aberrations (CA)

5. Species Identification (CA) - ring, terminal, isochromatic, multiple deletions, interchromosomal translocations, dicentric chromosomes
6. Identification of production sites, areas of high mutagenic background
7. Identification of chemicals and their combinations that form a mutagenic background
8. Study of dependence of level of induced mutagenesis from characteristics of substances
9. Research of reproductive health of women working at carcinogenic facilities
10. Clustering of industrial facilities by genotoxicity level⁹⁻¹³.

The object of observation is a line for production of cardboard and insulation tape. At the plant mutagenic background is formed by dibutyl phthalate, sulphuric acid, ethyl acetate, cyclohexane, hydrochloric acid, dioctylphthalene.

Short-term mutagenicity tests were performed at 12 points in the process and genotoxicity results were obtained:

Sample 1 - film production line. Number of metaphases 1070, number of aberrations 14, $M \pm m$ 1.32 ± 0.35 , types of aberrations - deletion, multiple lesions, eccentric ring, interchromosomal translocation. Comparison with control conditions showed a non-significant level of difference ($p > 0.05$).

Sample 2 - pellet production line, spreading. The number of metaphases 1075, the number of aberrations 14, $M \pm m$ 1.21 ± 0.35 , types of aberrations - deletion, multiple lesions, isochromatic deletion. Assessment of differences for the degree of reliability determined a non-significant level ($td = 1.25$, significance level $p > 0.05$).

In point 3, the film line, the rolling machine. Number of metaphases 1087, number of aberrations 15, $M \pm m$ 1.39 ± 0.35 , types of aberrations - deletion, multiple lesions, dicentric, acentric ring ($td = 1.57$, significance level $p > 0.05$, that is insufficient).

Point 4 - film line, mixer. Number of metaphases 1034, number of aberrations 21, $M \pm m$ 2.04 ± 0.44 , types of aberrations - deletion, multiple dicentric deletion ($td = 2.63$, significance level $p < 0.01$).

5 assay-film line, calender machine. Number of metaphases 1027, number of aberrations 12, $M \pm m$ 1.18 ± 0.35 ,

types of aberrations - deletion, multiple lesions, interchromosomal translocation (td = 1.13, significance level $p > 0.05$, i.e. insufficient level of difference).

6 Pressing assay. Number of metaphases 1088, number of aberrations 21, $M \pm m$ 1.94 ± 0.41 , type of aberrations - deletion, multiple lesions, isochromatic deletion, interchromosomal translocation (td = 2.52, significance level less than 0.005).

Sample 7 - Printed workshop. Number of metaphases 1015, number of aberrations 15, $M \pm m$ 1.49 ± 0.39 , types of aberrations - deletion, multiple deletion, dicentric (td = 1.72, significance level $p > 0.05$, that is insufficient).

Point 8-chemical workshop. Number of metaphases 1081, number of aberrations 20, $M \pm m$ 1.85 ± 0.41 , types of aberrations - deletion, multiple deletion, dicentric (td = 2.39, significance level $p < 0.05$, significant difference level).

9 point-sorting. Number of metaphases 1015, number of aberrations 22, $M \pm m$ 2.18 ± 0.47 , types of aberrations - deletion, dicentric, interchromosomal translocation, acentric ring, multiple deletion (td = 2.8, significance level $p < 0.01$).

10-point chromium chip break. Number of metaphases 1053, number of aberrations 19, $M \pm m$ 1.72 ± 0.4 , types of aberrations - deletion, multiple deletion, dicentric (td = 2.15, significance level < 0.05 , that is sufficient).

11 point - pellet production line, extruder. Number of metaphases 1037, number of aberrations 14, $M \pm m$ 1.36 ± 0.36 , types of aberrations - deletion, multiple deletion, eccentric ring (td = 1.49, significance level $p > 0.05$).

12 point - linoleic line. Number of metaphases 1039, number of aberrations 16, $M \pm m$ 1.55 ± 0.39 , types of aberrations - deletion, multiple deletion, interchromosomal translocation, eccentric ring (td = 1.86, significance level > 0.05).

Conclusions

The analysis of genotoxicity indicators made it possible to establish the sites of production line with reliably high levels of indicators in the form of number of metaphases, number of aberrations, types of aberrations. Mutagenic background at these sites is formed due to excretion and influence of chemical compounds dibutyl phthalate, sulphuric acid, ethyl acetate, cyclohexane, hydrochloric acid, dioctylphthalene vapours.

Correlation matrix allowed to establish correlation dependence of dioctylphthalene concentration on level of quantitative evaluation of aberrations ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.05$) and type of aberrations in form of terminal deletions ($r = 0.52$, $p < 0.05$).

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of statistical processing of indicators of genotoxicity and reproductive health disorders in workers, forms the basis for the clustering of industrial points, lines, technologies, etc.

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